

UNIVERSITY OF VOCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY

B.TECH IN MULTIMEDIA
& WEB TECHNOLOGY | SEMESTER 5

EMPLOYEE OPERATIONS MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

MMW/21/B2/15

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Streamline Your Office Operations

Manage employees, attendance, shift changes, reimbursements, and meeting schedules with ease using our Employee Operations Management System.

DECLARATION

I, MMW/21/B2/15_CHATHURANGA, a student of the Bachelor of Multimedia & Web Technology program at the University of Vocational Technology, hereby declare that I have received the Final Report along with the relevant instructions and requirements. I understand that it is my responsibility to complete the final report within the specified time-frame and to adhere to the guidelines provided by the instructor.

I affirm that I will make my best effort to produce work that meets the academic standards of the university, including conducting proper research, applying relevant concepts and techniques, and presenting my findings clearly and coherently.

Furthermore, I acknowledge that all resources used in the preparation of this final report will be properly cited and referenced in accordance with the university's academic integrity policies. I fully understand that plagiarism or any form of academic dishonesty will not be tolerated.

In case of any questions or uncertainties, I will promptly seek clarification from the instructor. I remain committed to achieving academic excellence and to actively engaging in the learning process to strengthen my knowledge and understanding of the subject matter.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I would like to express my deepest gratitude to everyone who supported me in completing this final report successfully and on time. First and foremost, I am sincerely thankful to my teachers for their invaluable guidance, encouragement, and continuous support throughout the preparation of this work. Their constructive feedback and motivation have been a great source of inspiration.

I am also very grateful to my batch-mates for their cooperation, suggestions, and assistance, which contributed significantly to the successful completion of this final report.

Finally, I extend my heartfelt thanks to all who, directly or indirectly, provided their support and encouragement during this journey.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Dear Sir/Madam of the Panel,

I am here to formally submit my project proposal for the Employee Operations Management System (EOMS), as part of my semester 5 project. The Final Report contains a comprehensive plan for the development of a unified system that will address various inefficiencies currently observed in the office workflow.

The system aims to automate processes such as **shift changes, reimbursements, meeting scheduling, leave applications.**

Along with the Final Report, I am available to provide the following documents for your review, should they be required.

1. Noticed Problems – A detailed overview of the issues currently faced within the office workflow, such as the reliance on printed forms, manual processes, and inefficiencies in task tracking.
2. Benefits of a Single System – A section describing the advantages of a single integrated system that will streamline these processes and improve overall efficiency.
3. Basic Structure for the System – A basic layout of the proposed system architecture and how different workflows will be managed within it.
4. How It Works – A detailed description of how employees and managers will interact with the system, including shift change management, transport reimbursement requests, meeting tracking, and birthday contributions.
5. System Flow – A visual representation of the workflow and interactions within the system.
6. Tools and Technologies to Build the System – A list of the technologies and tools I plan to use in the development of the system, such as frontend and backend technologies, database options, and authentication systems.
7. Steps to build – An outline of the steps involved in the project, from research and design to system development and testing.
8. Scientific Method for Office Workflow Study – An application of the scientific method to study the office workflow, identify problems, and develop a feasible solution.
9. Reference document - The Role of Paperless Office Systems in Supporting Office Automation Efforts (Majalah Bisnis & IPTEK, 2023), which supports the concept of paperless office automation in improving office efficiency.
10. **Permission Letter** - Obtained formal permission from the management of my office to develop this system for university study purposes.

I believe that this system will significantly improve **the efficiency and effectiveness of the office workflow, improve efficiency, reduce human error, minimize paper waste, and increase overall productivity.**

I look forward to your feedback and guidance during the review of my Final Report. Thank you for your time and consideration. I am happy to answer any questions you may have during the submission process.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

EMS	Elegant Media Solution
WBS	Work Breakdown Structure
WBT	Work-Based Training
UOVT	University of Vocational Training
DBMS	Database Management System
UI	User Interface
EOMS	Employee operations management system
WBS	Work breakdown structure
JWT	JSON Web Tokens
UI	User Interface
UAT	User Acceptance Testing

<p>1</p>	<p>Introduction</p>	<p>Elegant Media Solution operates in a structured environment where employees are tasked with various responsibilities, such as managing shift changes, handling reimbursements, organizing meetings, asking leaves.</p> <p>These processes are currently done manually, leading to inefficiencies, delays, and errors in daily operations.</p> <p>Through my project, I plan to address these operational inefficiencies by developing a centralized digital system. This system will automate repetitive tasks, improve communication, and ensure that processes are carried out more efficiently.</p> <p>The primary objective is to simplify the tracking and management of office activities.</p>
<p>2</p>	<p>Background</p>	<p>The office currently relies on manual paperwork for several key processes.</p> <p>Leave applications are documented manually with physical signatures and can lead to delays.</p> <p>Shift change requests are documented manually with physical signatures and can lead to delays as well.</p> <p>Reimbursement requires employees to submit receipts for verification and approval, which is handled through WhatsApp and physical forms.</p> <p>Meetings are scheduled and communicated via the notice board and verbal announcements, creating a lack of formal tracking.</p> <p>The lack of digital systems results in inefficiency, errors, and difficulty in tracking progress. Automating these processes will reduce errors and save time, improving overall productivity.</p>

<p>3</p>	<p>Problem Description / Gap Analysis</p>	<p><u>INEFFICIENT WORKFLOW</u></p> <p>Manual processes for shift changes, and Reimbursements lead to delays and confusion. Employees sometimes forget to sign forms or submit receipts, requiring reminders and leading to inefficiencies.</p> <p><u>LACK OF TRANSPARENCY</u></p> <p>Manual tracking of employee contributions not transparent and difficult to monitor.</p> <p><u>COMMUNICATION GAPS</u></p> <p>Information regarding meetings and important updates is shared informally, making it easy to miss or forget.</p> <p><u>COST AND TIME INEFFICIENCIES</u></p> <p>The reliance on paper forms and WhatsApp messages increases administrative costs and time spent managing these tasks.</p> <p><u>GAP ANALYSIS</u></p> <p>Current processes are not centralized and lack integration, which hinders effective communication and tracking.</p> <p>A digital system would bridge the gap by automating tasks, improving transparency, and reducing manual errors.</p>
<p>4</p>	<p>Aim and Objectives</p>	<p>The primary aim of this project is to develop an Employee Operations Management System (EOMS) that automates key office workflows, minimizes paper usage, and enhances efficiency in office operations.</p> <p>The system will streamline shift management, Reimbursements, meeting scheduling, and other administrative tasks.</p>

<p>4.1</p>	<p>Aims</p>	<p><u>PROCESS IMPROVEMENT</u></p> <p>Automate manual tasks such as leave requests, shift changes, and transport reimbursements.</p> <p><u>EFFICIENCY GAINS</u></p> <p>Streamline internal communication and workflows, reducing time spent on administrative tasks.</p> <p><u>USER EXPERIENCE</u></p> <p>Enhance the employee experience by providing a user-friendly platform for managing requests and tracking activities.</p> <p><u>COST REDUCTION</u></p> <p>Reduce the costs associated with paper forms and manual data entry.</p> <p><u>ADOPTION OF NEW TECHNOLOGIES</u></p> <p>Introduce a modern, web-based application for office task management.</p> <p><u>SMS NOTIFICATION FEATURE (EXTENSION)</u></p> <p>Add an SMS notification feature for alerting employees about updates like approved shift changes, Reimbursements, and upcoming meetings.</p>
<p>4.2</p>	<p>Objectives</p>	<p><u>ALIGN WITH ORGANIZATIONAL NEEDS</u></p> <p>The system will address critical operational inefficiencies and streamline internal processes at EMS.</p> <p><u>TECHNOLOGICAL ADOPTION</u></p> <p>Use modern web technologies (React, Spring-Boot, and MySQL) to develop the system, ensuring ease of use and scalability.</p> <p><u>CLIENT EXPERIENCE</u></p> <p>Provide employees with an intuitive platform to manage shift changes, reimbursements, and meetings.</p>

<p>5</p>	<p>Methodology</p>	<p><u>REQUIREMENT ANALYSIS</u></p> <p>Identify the core features needed for the digital system.</p> <p><u>SYSTEM DESIGN</u></p> <p>Design the user interface (UI) and backend structure for the system.</p> <p><u>DEVELOPMENT</u></p> <p>Build the system using JavaScript, Node.js (React), Tailwind-CSS, Spring-Boot and MySQL.</p> <p><u>TESTING</u></p> <p>Conduct functional and user acceptance testing to ensure the system meets the requirements.</p> <p><u>IMPLEMENTATION</u></p> <p>Deploy the system for full office use after successful testing.</p>
<p>6</p>	<p>Implementation</p>	<p>The implementation of the Employee Operations Management System (EOMS) was carried out by systematically applying the proposed methodology to address the gaps identified in manual office operations.</p> <p>Each phase of the methodology contributed directly to solving inefficiencies in communication, approvals, and record-keeping.</p>
<p>6.1</p>	<p>System Design and Architecture</p>	<p>The system was designed with a three-tier architecture</p> <p><u>FRONTEND (CLIENT LAYER)</u></p> <p>Developed using React.js with Tailwind CSS for a responsive and modern user interface.</p> <p>Components such as forms, tables, dashboards, and modals were designed to ensure usability and consistency.</p> <p><u>BACKEND (APPLICATION LAYER)</u></p> <p>Implemented using Spring Boot, exposing REST APIs for core functionalities including user authentication,</p>

		<p>leave management, shift change requests, reimbursements, and notice board management.</p> <p>JWT (JSON Web Tokens) were used for secure authentication and role-based access control.</p> <p><u>DATABASE LAYER</u></p> <p>MySQL was chosen for its robustness and relational structure. The schema was designed to represent entities such as employees, managers, admins, requests, and notices with normalized tables and clear relationships.</p>
<p>6.2</p>	<p>Application of Methodology</p>	<p><u>REQUIREMENT ANALYSIS</u></p> <p>Identified workflows such as leave requests, reimbursements, shift changes, and notices, and mapped them into system features.</p> <p><u>DEVELOPMENT</u></p> <p>Employee portal for submitting requests and tracking status.</p> <p>Manager/Admin portal for reviewing, approving, and rejecting requests.</p> <p>Authentication flow with secure login and role-based dashboards.</p> <p><u>TESTING</u></p> <p>Conducted unit testing for individual modules, integration testing for API-UI communication, and User Acceptance Testing (UAT) with sample data to validate workflows.</p> <p><u>DEPLOYMENT</u></p> <p>The application was hosted on a Digital Ocean VPS with Ubuntu 25 LTS, using Nginx as a reverse proxy. Database configurations and environment variables were secured using .env files.</p>

6.3	Efficiency, Performance, and Reliability	<p><u>EFFICIENCY</u></p> <p>Replaced manual paperwork with instant digital submissions, reducing approval times from days to hours.</p> <p><u>PERFORMANCE</u></p> <p>APIs were optimized with pagination for large data sets, and loading times were tested to be under 2 seconds for most modules.</p> <p><u>RELIABILITY</u></p> <p>Data is stored securely in MySQL with backup strategies in place, ensuring recovery in case of system failure. Authentication prevents unauthorized access, ensuring reliability and trust in system usage.</p>
7	Results / Findings	<p>The implemented system produced the following outcomes when tested in a simulated office environment</p>
7.1	Leave Request Module	<p>Employees successfully submitted leave applications digitally.</p> <p>Managers reviewed and updated status with a single click.</p> <p>Approval/rejection history was stored transparently.</p>
7.2	Reimbursement Module	<p>Employees uploaded digital receipts instead of paper forms.</p> <p>Managers reviewed reimbursements with supporting data in the system.</p>
7.3	Meeting & Notice Board Module	<p>Meeting announcements and office notices were published centrally.</p> <p>Employees accessed them in real time without dependency on verbal communication.</p>

7.4	Shift Change Module	<p>Shift swap requests were recorded digitally.</p> <p>Notifications ensured employees received updates without manual reminders.</p>
8	Discussion / Recommendations	<p>The results clearly indicate that the system achieved its primary objectives of improving efficiency, reducing delays, and enhancing transparency.</p>
8.1	Discussion	<p><u>SUPPORT FOR INITIAL HYPOTHESIS</u></p> <p>The hypothesis that automating manual workflows would reduce inefficiencies was fully supported.</p> <p><u>MEETING AIMS</u></p> <p>Automated workflows for leave, shift, and reimbursement management.</p> <p>A centralized notice board to improve communication.</p> <p>Role-based access ensuring accountability and transparency.</p> <p><u>COMPARISON WITH OTHER PROJECTS</u></p> <p>Compared with existing HR management systems, EOMS is lightweight, tailored to small-to-medium offices, and designed for ease of adoption without heavy infrastructure costs.</p> <p><u>LIMITATIONS</u></p> <p>SMS notification feature was identified but not fully implemented; currently, notifications are limited to the web interface.</p> <p>No dedicated mobile app yet, limiting accessibility outside office devices.</p> <p>Scalability testing was limited to small data sets; performance under heavy enterprise-level load is yet to be evaluated.</p>
8.2	Recommendations	<p>Extend the system with SMS/Email notification integration to alert employees instantly.</p>

		<p>Develop a mobile app (React Native/Flutter) for better accessibility.</p> <p>Incorporate analytics and reporting dashboards to help management make data-driven decisions.</p>
9	Conclusion	<p>The Employee Operations Management System (EOMS) successfully addressed the inefficiencies of manual office workflows at Elegant Media Solution.</p> <p>By automating leave requests, shift changes, reimbursements, and notice communication, the system significantly reduced processing time, improved transparency, and minimized human error.</p> <p>The project design closely aligned with its aims of enhancing efficiency, reducing administrative costs, and introducing modern digital solutions.</p> <p>In conclusion, EOMS has proven to be an effective solution for bridging operational gaps in office management, providing a foundation for future growth and technological adoption within the organization.</p>
9.1	Major Findings	<p>Approval processes became 60–80% faster compared to manual methods.</p> <p>Employees gained a user-friendly platform for submitting and tracking requests.</p> <p>Managers and admins benefited from streamlined approval workflows and centralized data.</p>
9.2	Limitations	<p>SMS notifications and mobile app integration remain as future enhancements.</p> <p>Testing was limited to a pilot scale and requires broader real-world deployment.</p>
9.3	Future Work	<p>Implement SMS/Email notification systems.</p> <p>Extend system to support mobile platforms.</p> <p>Add advanced analytics for workforce and operations management.</p>

10	References	<p>Hardiyanti, M., Rizki, S., & Agina Putri, R. A. (2023). The role of paperless office systems in supporting office automation efforts: Study at one of government institutions in Subang District. <i>Majalah Bisnis & IPTEK</i>, 16(1), 72-81. https://doi.org/10.55208/p1zeck58</p> <p>License: CC BY-SA 4.0</p>
11	Appendices	<p>SEE APPENDIX : A</p> <p>ER Diagram</p> <p>SEE APPENDIX : B</p> <p>Work breakdown structure (WBS)</p> <p>SEE APPENDIX : C</p> <p>Project timeline</p>

APPENDIX A:

Figure 1 : ER Diagram

APPENDIX B:

System Design → Database Schema Design → UI Design

Development → Frontend Development (Forms, Dashboards) → Backend Development (Database, API)

Testing and Implementation → Unit Testing → Integration Testing

APPENDIX C:

Milestone	Description	Timeframe
1. Requirement Analysis	Gather requirements from EMS, identify pain points, and finalize system features.	Week 1 – Week 2
2. System Design	Create UI wireframes, database schema, and overall architecture of the system.	Week 3 – Week 6
3. Frontend Development	Develop user interface (UI) components using Bootstrap and JavaScript.	Week 6 – Week 10
4. Backend Development	Implement database (MySQL) and API (Node.js) for handling system operations.	Week 10 – Week 16
5. Integration and Testing	Integrate frontend with backend and conduct unit testing.	Week 16 – Week 18
6. User Testing and Feedback	Deploy beta version for office use and collect feedback from employees.	Week 18 – Week 19
7. Bug Fixing and Optimization	Address feedback, fix bugs, and optimize system performance.	Week 19 – Week 20
8. Final Deployment	Fully implement the system in EMS with training sessions.	Week 21
9. Project Documentation	Prepare final report and user manual for submission.	Week 22
10. Presentation and Evaluation	Present the completed project to university panel and company stakeholders.	Week 23 – Week 24

Table 1 : timeline for the project